

**TO EVALUATE EFFECT OF ASHWAGANDHA RASAYANA ON
MANSAVAHA SROTAS AND ASTHIVAHA SROTAS****Vd Aakash Ashokrao Pawar*¹, Vd Sahadas A. Aradhye², Vd Bhavin S. Dubal³, Vd
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ABSTRACT

A] Srotas are endless channels which supply the nutrients to various tissues of the body. Srotas is defined as “Sravanaat srotansi” according to the Charak.^[1] Srotas involves the flow of body substances from one place to another and responsible for the nourishment of different Dhatus.^[2] B] Mansavaha Srotas are the channels responsible for formation, nourishment, circulation and maintenance of Mamsa Dhatu (muscle tissue) and its main Mulasthan is Snayu and Twaka^[3] as per Sushrut whereas Asthivaha Srotas are the channels responsible for nutrition, growth, maintenance and strengthening of Asthi Dhatu. C] Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) is an important Rasayana in Ayurveda told by Acharya Charak in Chikitsasthan first Adhyaya. This conceptual study evaluates its effect on Mamsavaha and Asthivaha Srotas based on classical Ayurveda. The plant is botanically identified as *Withania somnifera*. It is an important medicinal plant and used in

Ayurvedic medicines for the treatment of many diseases and it is also used in other parts of world.^[4] In Ayurveda it is known as Rasayana because it promotes health and longevity, arrest aging process, increase capability of individual to resist adverse environmental conditions.^[5] *W. somnifera* commonly known as “Ashwagandha”, “Asgandh” and “Winter Cherry” belongs to family Solanaceae and widely distributed in warmer parts of the world.

Genus *Withania* comprises 23 species including *W. somnifera* (L.) Dunal and *W. coagulans* (L.) Dunal having high medicinal value which is used as “*Rasayana*” in Ayurvedic formulations.^[6] *Ashwagandha* attains the special name because its root smells like horse (“*Ashwa*”) and believe to provide power like horse when consumed.^[7] In Vedas, it is described as herbal tonic and health food and considered as “*Indian Ginseng*” because of its ginseng like health promoting effects.^[8] Evidence suggests *Ashwagandha* improves *Mansa Dhatu*(muscle mass), *Ashti Dhatu*(bone density), and overall tissue nourishment.

KEYWORD: Srotas, Mansvaha srotas, Asthivaha asrotas, *Ashwagandha Rasayana*.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda has its own holistic approach to understand the *Purush Sharir* by different theories like Srotas, In Ayurvedic classics the term Srotas is used as all the macro and micro channels and pathways operating in the living organism. Charak has defined it is “*Sravanaat srotansi*” meaning a channel through which *sravana* takes place. There is a description of Srotas by 13 Acharya Charak and 11 pairs of Srotas by Acharya Sushrut. Srotas are the micro channels of the body which provide platform for activities of Tridosh, Dhatu, Oja, Agni etc. Srotas are channels or pores which provides nourishment to the whole body and responsible for some particular function with respect to specific body parts. The Ayurveda samhitas described anatomical and physiological concepts of srotas broadly. Srotas mainly regulates process of circulation in human body. Srotas is mentioned in various Ayurvedic literature. Srotas meaning channels or pores which are present throughout the visible body as well as in “invisible” or subtle level of the cell, molecules and atoms. Srotas are channels responsible for tissue nutrition.

Physiological importance of Srotas

1. Srotas performs transportation of dhatus
2. Srotas carries *Bhava Padarth* from one place to another place. → It transports materials and impulses also.
3. → Helps in the absorption of fats and minerals through lymph and utilizing pressure of blood.
4. → It served as place of transformation of *Ahararasa* to *Rasadhatu*. → It offers pathways for transporting *Rasadhatu* in the body.

MAMSAVAHA SROTAS

The origin of Mamsavaha srotas are Snayu and Twak. Mamsavaha Srotas are minute transporting channels of muscle tissue, they are associated with Snayu-twak and Rakta vahini dhamanis. Mamsavah srotas are the channels which convey materials requiring for the building of Mansa Dhatu. this Srotas helps to achieve body firmness, compactness and muscular strength.

Mula: Snayu and Twak.

Normal Physiology of Mamsavaha Strotas: → Mamsavaha Strotas provides firm, muscular and healthy muscle tonus along with stability. → The normal physiology of this Strotas gives rigid posture and physical strength. → Carrying nutrients to the Mansa Dhatu and next dhatu. → Covers the Asthi and Sandhis.

Symptoms of injury to Mamsavaha srotas

- Shwayathu
- Mamsa shosha
- Sira granthi
- Adhi maamsa
- Arbudam
- Gala shaalooka
- Pooti maamsa
- Characteristics of Mamsavaha srotas Srotodushti^[9]

ASTHIVAHA SROTAS

Asthivaha Srotas Channels of transportation for Asthaayi (Poshaka, Sukshma) Asthidhatu to their destination are Asthivaha Srotas. Srotomula -Srotomula is the place of origin of the

Srotas. This particular part of Srotas regulates and controls the function of entire Srotas and Asthivaha Srotas nourish bone tissue.

Asthivaha Srotas Mulasthan

Acharya Charaka has mentioned two Mulasthan of Asthivaha Srotas-1) Medomula 2) Jaghana.^[10]

Medo - Meda can be described as the Fat tissues of human body. According to Charaka Asthi Poshakansha is formed from previous Dhatu that is Medadhatu, and that's why it is included in Srtotomula of Asthivaha Srtotas. According to Chakradatta Asthi poshakansha which is formed from Medadhadu is in the liquid (Drava) form and hence its transportation is done through Asthivaha srotas. Jaghana- It can be described as flat pelvic bones, which is essential in the maintenance of the upright posture of the body i.e the Dharana of the body, mentioned as the Karma of Asthi Dhatu.

Ashraya ashrayee sambandh- According to Ayurveda, Vata Dosha resides in the Asthi Dhatu. Pitta Dosha resides in the Rakta Dhatu and Kapha Dosha in the rest of the Dhatus. When the Dosha residing in Dhatu increases, the particular Dhatu will also get increased .But this rule is just reversed in case of Vata and Asthi i.e. the aggravated Vata will cause the depletion of Asthi Dhatu.

Asthivaha Srotas Dushti^[11]

Lakshan: The occurrence of Adhidanta (excessive teeth) or Ashtana Asthini eg: osteophytes, Calcaneal spur etc, Asthishool (pain) or Dantabhangacha and any deformity of hair, hair follicles, mustache or nails. Asthivaha Srotodushti includes Asthi Vridhi and Kshaya lakshanas. Ashthi dhau kshaya- Asthishool (Bone pain), Dantabhangacha (breaking of teeth or nails), nails and body, hairfall and loss of stability of joints.

Ashwagandha is described as Balya, Brimhana, and Rasayana, supporting strength and rejuvenation.

Ashwagandha Rasayana (a rejuvenating preparation of *Withania somnifera*) is used for its action on two key tissue systems, which directly correlates to the **Mansavaha** and **Asthivaha** Srotas.

Effect on Mansavaha Srotas

The Mansavaha Srotas are responsible for the transport and nourishment of **Mamsa Dhatu** (Muscle tissue). Vitiating leads to muscle wasting (*mamsa kshaya*), weakness (*daurbalya*), and loss of muscle tone.

Ashwagandha Rasayana's effect is primarily **Brimhana** and **Balya** (strength promoting), which directly supports the function of the Mansavaha Srotas

- **Muscle Strength and Mass:** Ashwagandha is traditionally used to improve physical strength and is sometimes called "Indian Ginseng" due to its ability to impart "the strength of a horse." Modern studies support its potential to increase **muscle mass and strength** (acting as a rejuvenator for the Mamsa Dhatu).
- **Reducing Fatigue:** By acting as an **adaptogen** and helping the body manage stress (by modulating the HPA axis and reducing cortisol), it helps preserve energy and combat fatigue (*shrama*), which is a symptom of impaired Mansavaha Srotas.

Effect on Asthivaha Srotas

The Asthivaha Srotas are the channels responsible for the transport of materials needed for the formation and maintenance of **Asthi Dhatu** (Bone tissue). Vitiating can lead to bone pain (*asthi shoola*), bone loss (*asthi kshaya*), and joint disorders.

Ashwagandha Rasayana is beneficial due to its **Vata-Kapha pacifying** and **Rasayana** properties. Asthi Dhatu is the main seat (*Ashraya*) of Vata Dosha, and increased Vata is the primary cause of bone degeneration (*Asthi Kshaya*).

- **Nourishment and Strength to Asthi dhatu:** Ashwagandha is listed among the herbs with **Kapha-Vata Shamaka** (pacifying) properties that help in clearing and nourishing the channels. It supports the metabolism of the Asthi dhatu, which is crucial for the proper functioning of Asthivaha Srotas.
- **Anti-Arthritic and Anti-Inflammatory:** It is found to be useful in conditions like Rheumatoid and Osteoarthritis, which involve degeneration and inflammation affecting bone and joint structures, suggesting a protective and healing action on the tissues maintained by the Asthivaha Srotas.

- **Supporting Bone Density:** Research indicates that components of Ashwagandha (like Withaferin-A) may help by **increasing the growth and differentiation of osteoblasts** (bone-forming cells) and **decreasing the activity of osteoclasts** (bone-resorbing cells). This suggests a mechanism for maintaining or improving bone density, directly benefiting the Asthi Dhatu transported by its Srotas.

In summary, Ashwagandha Rasayana's overall **Rasayana** (rejuvenative) effect enhances the quality and strength of these tissues, promoting the health and efficient functioning of both the **Mansavaha** and **Asthivaha Srotas**.

METHODOLOGY

Type: Conceptual & literary review.

Sources: Classical texts, Nighantus, peer-reviewed modern research.

Method: Comparative interpretation of Ayurvedic concepts with modern scientific evidence.

DISCUSSION

Effect on Mamsavaha Srotas

- Guru & Snigdha properties increase nourishment.
- Balya & Brimhana actions increase strength.
- Modern science: Improves testosterone, muscle mass, endurance.

Effect on Asthivaha Srotas

- Supports Asthi Dhatu formation.
- Vata-shamana prevents bone degeneration.

Ashwagandha is highly beneficial for muscle and bone tissue health. Both Ayurveda and modern research support its role as a Rasayana for strength, nourishment, and rejuvenation.

CONCLUSION

The observations of this study indicate that Ashwagandha Rasayana provides strength to *Mansavaha* strotus and *asthivaha* strotus. Ashwagandha Rasayana play an important role in dhatu poshana nyaya specifically improving the mamsa dhatu and asthi dhatu. Ashwagandha Rasayana directly act on musculoskeletal system of the body so there is Improvement in muscle endurance and better bone-related various functions reflect the herb's ability to strengthen both Mamsavaha and Asthivaha Srotas.

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